

BLAST WAVE MITIGATION USING DISSIPATIVE ELASTIC METAMATERIALS

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ABSTRACT

Elastic metamaterials have been intensively studied in recent years due to their unusual properties in manipulating elastic waves which are not readily available in nature. In the paper, an elastic metamaterial with two dissipative resonators is presented for blast-wave and broadband wave mitigation. The concepts of negative effective mass and how the dissipative mass-in-mass system to create a broadband gap are explained in detail. Numerical simulations are performed to reveal the working mechanism and wave absorption ability of the proposed metamaterial. It can be found that a wide bandgap could be achieved by properly selecting the damping coefficients. Finally, a physical structure is suggested to actively control the damping coefficients, thus providing tunable attenuation capabilities. The results of the study could be used in developing new navy sandwich structures for blast wave mitigation which may cause severe local damage to the hull or material failure by fatigue.

1 INTRODUCTION

In recent years, a great deal of numerical and experimental research focused on blast induced shock waves (SW) behavior in various homo- and heterogeneous materials has been conducted with the goal of developing practical mechanisms for SW mitigation. The topical interest has been brought about due to an array of integrative applications including civilian and military utilizations, both focused on efficient SW attenuation. A range of material and structural configurations have been proposed and investigated by researchers for their potential uses as a SW attenuation mechanism. Li and Meng carried out numerical investigations of the elastic wave response of a solid-phase cellular material (CM) subjected to compressive SW's by employing a one-dimensional (1D) spring-mass lattice model [1]. While it was concluded that non-linear dissipation in the CM reduced the energy and momentum of the propagating stress wave, the peak pressure could be amplified. This model could be considered as a viable solution if the goal is to mitigate energy and momentum, however, if the subsequent pressure induced is of greater concern the use of CM's is impractical. Nesterenko reached a similar conclusion in his investigation of "soft" condensed matter [2]. Again, analyzing a simple 1D spring-mass system it was demonstrated that granular or porous materials could be tailored for effective energy and momentum absorption of a SW with the same amplification of pressure transmission through the material. Del Prete et al. carried out numerical analysis and experimental studies on the mitigation of blast waves by dry aqueous foams by employing a multiphase model [3]. Su et al. conducted numerical and experimental analysis of a piston-cylinder device that was capable of SW mitigation [4,5]. The assembly functioned by inducing reflection of the SW within the hydraulic cylinder containing compressible fluid to effectively mitigate the wave transmission through the structure. However, in the process of "containing" the SW, the duration of pressure transmitted through the base of the cylinder was increased. Chen et al proposed a blast wave mitigation mechanism that employs a liquid filled, compressible plastic membrane, which utilizes a pressure release feature to serve as a kinetic energy transformer by redirecting the incident pressure wave [6]. Through experimental findings it was shown that the pressure redirect system was able to substantially mitigate the transmitted pressure associated with the impinging SW on an object behind the liquid reservoir.

The realm of elastic metamaterial (EMM) research is a relatively new field that presents exciting and novel applications related to wave propagation and attenuation due to their properties which do not occur in any existing natural materials. By using a mass-in-mass lattice to represent an EMM it was found that negative effective mass density could be achieved [7]. Regarding the application of EMM's as a method of SW mitigation, the key drawback is the local resonance mechanism and fixed band gap inherent in a passive EMM. Because of this characteristic, passive EMM's are only effective for wave attenuation in a relatively low frequency domain. In an effort to improve the wave attenuation performance in broadband frequencies, a model consisting of multi-resonator was investigated under harmonic wave excitation [8]. A similar multi-resonator model was adopted and used to explore the possibility for blast wave mitigation [9]. Manimala et al. modified the model further by analyzing dissipative EMM microstructures in order to allow for wave attenuation over a broader spectrum of excitation frequencies [10-12]. A dissipative mechanism in a single resonator was also utilized in order to act as a broadband vibration absorber for elastic waves in elastic metamaterial beams where numerical simulations indicated the presence of a stopband effect [13,14]. Zhu et al. investigated the vibration suppression abilities of a chiral EMM with multiple resonators, both analytically and experimentally, in the hopes of producing broadband vibration suppression [15].

In this paper, a dissipative EMM with two resonators is designed and quantitatively analyzed for blast wave broadband mitigation. Wave dispersion relations of a dissipative lattice system with two resonators is investigated. A wide wave attenuation band has been found through properly selecting the damping coefficient of the innermost damper. Transient analysis of the proposed lattice system subjected to a blast pulse is performed to demonstrate the efficiency of its application in blast wave mitigation. Finally, a physical structure is suggested to actively control the damping coefficients, thus providing tunable attenuation capabilities. The efficiency of the proposed dissipative EMM for blast wave mitigation is examined numerically. The results of the study could be used in developing new navy sandwich structures for blast wave mitigation.

2 DISSIPATIVE MASS-IN-MASS LATTICE SYSTEM WITH TWO RESONATORS

2.1 Wave dispersion analysis

An infinitely long one-dimensional lattice system consisting of periodic spring-mass-damper unit cells is now considered in Fig. 1. Each unit cell contains two local resonators and is separated from each of its adjacent cells by a length, L . The three rigid masses that make up each of the unit cells are m_1 , m_2 , and m_3 , respectively. Each of the unit cells are connected by a spring and damper with coefficients k_1 and c_1 , while k_2 and c_2 represent the interfaces between the middle mass and the outer mass which act as spring and damping coefficients, respectively. The spring and damping coefficients, k_3 and c_3 , represent the interfaces between the innermost mass and the middle mass, respectively. This model is an extension to the multi-resonator model developed by Huang and Sun [8] which only investigated the effects of the spring stiffness coefficients.

For the dissipative multi-resonator structure, equations of motion for the j -th unit cell can be derived as

$$m_1 \frac{d^2 u_1^{(j)}}{dt^2} + k_1 [2u_1^{(j)} - u_1^{(j-1)} - u_1^{(j+1)}] + c_1 \left[2 \frac{du_1^{(j)}}{dt} - \frac{du_1^{(j-1)}}{dt} - \frac{du_1^{(j+1)}}{dt} \right] + k_2 [u_1^{(j)} - u_2^{(j)}] + c_2 \left[\frac{du_1^{(j)}}{dt} - \frac{du_2^{(j)}}{dt} \right] = 0 \quad (1a)$$

$$m_2 \frac{d^2 u_2^{(j)}}{dt^2} + k_2 [u_2^{(j)} - u_1^{(j)}] + c_2 \left[\frac{du_2^{(j)}}{dt} - \frac{du_1^{(j)}}{dt} \right] + k_3 [u_2^{(j)} - u_3^{(j)}] + c_3 \left[\frac{du_2^{(j)}}{dt} - \frac{du_3^{(j)}}{dt} \right] = 0 \quad (1b)$$

$$m_3 \frac{d^2 u_3^{(j)}}{dt^2} + k_3 [u_3^{(j)} - u_2^{(j)}] + c_3 \left[\frac{du_3^{(j)}}{dt} - \frac{du_2^{(j)}}{dt} \right] = 0 \quad (1c)$$

where $u_\alpha^{(j)}$ is defined with respect to its equilibrium position, as the displacement of mass " α " ($\alpha = 1, 2, \text{ or } 3$) in the j -th unit cell of the lattice. According to the Bloch theorem, the harmonic waveform of displacement for the j -th unit cell is given as [7,8]

$$u_\alpha^{(j)} = B_\alpha e^{i(qx - \omega t)} \quad (2)$$

where B_α is the complex amplitude of the wave, q is the wavenumber, and ω is the angular frequency. By substituting Eq. (2) into Eq. (1), the wave dispersion relations can be obtained by setting the determinant of the system equal to zero as

$$\begin{vmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{13} \\ A_{21} & A_{22} & A_{23} \\ A_{31} & A_{32} & A_{33} \end{vmatrix} = 0 \quad (3a)$$

in which,

$$A_{11} = -\theta_1 \Omega^2 + 2(\delta_1 + i\Omega\Gamma_1)(1 - \cos qL) + 1 + i\Omega\Gamma_2 \quad (3b)$$

$$A_{12} = A_{21} = -1 - i\Omega\Gamma_2 \quad (3c)$$

$$A_{13} = A_{31} = 0 \quad (3d)$$

$$A_{22} = -\Omega^2 + 1 + i\Omega\Gamma_2 + \delta_3 + i\Omega\Gamma_3 \quad (3e)$$

$$A_{23} = A_{32} = -\delta_3 - i\Omega\Gamma_3 \quad (3f)$$

$$A_{33} = -\theta_3 \Omega^2 + \delta_3 + i\Omega\Gamma_3 \quad (3g)$$

where $\Omega = \omega/\omega_0$ is the non-dimensional frequency with $\omega_0 = \sqrt{k_2/m_2}$. The mass and stiffness ratios are defined as $\theta_1 = m_1/m_2$, $\theta_3 = m_3/m_2$, $\delta_1 = k_1/k_2$ and $\delta_3 = k_3/k_2$. The non-dimensionalized damping parameters for the inner, middle and outer masses are given as $\tau_1 = C_1/C_0$, $\tau_2 = C_2/C_0$ and $\tau_3 = C_3/C_0$, respectively, where $C_0 = \sqrt{k_2 m_2}$.

Figure 1: Dissipative mass-in-mass lattice system with two resonators.

In order to investigate the effects of the dissipative mass-in-mass lattice system on the blast wave attenuation behavior, numerical calculations were carried out. Prior studies have already shown that the attenuation abilities of a two-resonator EMM can be improved by increasing the internal mass of the unit cell [8]. By varying the damping values of the system, while the values for the mass and stiffness ratios remain constant ($\theta_1 = 0.2$, $\theta_3 = 4$, $\delta_1 = 5$ and $\delta_3 = 0.5$), it is possible to see the influence of the dissipation on wave attenuation performance.

First, the effect of the middle damper's magnitude, τ_2 , is examined, while the innermost damper is removed entirely from the system ($\tau_3 = 0$). Analyzing the wavenumber of a dissipative material as a function of Ω , which is a real number in nature, results in a complex wavenumber that takes the form, $qL = \alpha + i\beta$ with α and β representing the propagation and attenuation parts of the wave, respectively. The results for the real and imaginary components of the wavenumber are shown in Figs. 2 (a) and (b) respectively. In the Fig. 2 (a), two perfect band gaps are present, when the material is treated as a non-dissipative metamaterial ($\tau_2 = \tau_3 = 0$). The first band gap is relatively narrow in the low frequency region, while the second is broad in the higher frequency domain. As τ_2 is increased to be greater than zero, it is obvious that the band gap in the higher frequency range begins to disappear signifying that the previously evanescent wave is now able to propagate through the EMM. However, the band gap occupying the lower frequency range is nearly unaffected, where the group velocity is close to zero. Furthermore, waves in the frequency range between the two band gaps mostly remain the same group

velocity as that in the non-dissipative EMM. Finally, when $\tau_2 = 10$, the connection between m_1 and m_2 approaches rigid, and the wave propagation behavior becomes similar to a conventional one resonator metamaterial. As shown in Fig. 2 (b), wave attenuation behaviors affected by τ_2 can be clearly illustrated. When damping effects are totally suppressed ($\tau_2 = \tau_3 = 0$), two clear wave attenuation regions can be observed at the corresponding band gap frequencies. Waves at other frequencies can propagate through the EMM without mitigation. As the damping ratio τ_2 is increased from zero to a positive number, wave attenuation abilities become weaker at the lower frequency range of the second band gap but stronger at higher frequencies. As previously found in Fig. 2 (a), the effects of τ_2 on the first band gap at low frequency domain are negligible. Wave mitigation at the frequency region between the two band gaps is unable to be perceived for any τ_2 in the figure. For $\tau_2 = 10$, besides the first attenuation band, waves can also be mitigated at much higher frequencies. It can be concluded that the magnitude of the middle damper contributes a lot to the wave mitigation at the frequencies higher than the second band gap, whereas it will be functionless at other lower frequencies under these mass and stiffness ratios.

Figure 2: Dispersion relations of the dissipative mass-in-mass lattice system with two resonators.

Similarly, in Figs. 2 (c) and (d) the effect of the innermost damper, τ_3 , is analyzed by setting the middle damper's magnitude to zero ($\tau_2 = 0$), other parameters remain the same with those used in Figs. 2 (a) and (b). Different from that observed in Figs. 2 (a) and (b), τ_3 can alert wave propagation and attenuation behaviors at frequencies lower than the second band gap. There are no obvious changes observed until τ_3 is increased from 0 to 0.1. The most interesting findings are the emerge of the first and second attenuation regions, when $\tau_3 = 1$. The real component of the wavenumber in Fig. 2 (c) illustrates that the group velocity within this emerged region is closed to zero, and the wave energy flow rate is therefore tiny. It can also be found that wave attenuation is strong over the whole emerged region as represented by β in Fig. 2 (d). This significantly enlarged wave attenuation region would be of great

help to applications of broadband wave mitigation. Specifically, when $\tau_3 = 10$, the connection between m_2 and m_3 will be nearly rigid, and these two masses will be composed into a big inner mass to function as a single resonator in the lattice system. The newly formed attenuation region is narrower than that with $\tau_3 = 1$. However, waves will be attenuated quickly at lower frequencies within the band gap.

2.2 Transient analysis of the proposed system under harmonic and blast waves

In order to further reveal the working mechanism of the proposed dissipative lattice system in time domain, a transient analysis with harmonic incidence is performed by using the commercial finite element software, ANSYS. In Fig. 3, we constructed a 1-D lattice system, which composed 600 proposed EMMs connected with each other through k_1 and c_1 . In the simulation, a longitudinal harmonic prescribed displacement boundary condition, $u_1^{(1)} = u_0 \sin(2\pi ft)$, is applied to the outer mass, m_1 , in the first unit cell, and m_1 in the 600-th unit cell is fixed. The COMBIN40 element is selected, which performs as a combination of a spring and damper in parallel and a mass in one node.

Figure 3: 1-D dissipative mass-in-mass lattice system under a harmonic incidence.

Figure 4 shows the total work done by the reaction force, total energy within the first unit cell and energy transmissions at the first, 5th and 15th unit cell at different frequencies, when the damping is removed from the EMM. In the simulation, $m_2 = 0.01$ kg and $\omega_0 = 2000$ Hz, other mass and stiffness ratios remain unchanged as those used in Fig. 2. Based on the given parameters of the non-dissipative EMM, two resonant frequencies can be calculated, which are 569.1 Hz and 2485.2 Hz. Wave energy behaviors have been examined at five different frequencies, which are 572 Hz, 1000 Hz, 2000 Hz, 2490 Hz and 3500 Hz in Figs. 4 (a) – (e), respectively. By applying frequency values that fall within the band gaps and near the resonant frequencies (i.e. 572 Hz and 2490 Hz in Figs. 4 (a) and (d)), wave phenomena is observed to be identical. From these two figures, it is seen that the work done is almost temporarily stored within the 1st unit cell before being nearly fully extracted by the negative work done. Small amount of energy that is leaking from the 1st cell to the proceeding unit cells and is equal to the difference between the work done and energy within the 1st cell. The energy leaking becomes nearly negligible, as the time increased. This mechanism can be applied directly in proceeding unit cells in the lattice system as is shown in the energy transmission through the 5th and 15th unit cells. It is obvious that almost no energy is transmitted from either of these two cells to the remaining lattice. This behavior is in good agreement with the results presented in Figs. 2 (b) and (d), where large amplitude for the imaginary portion of the wavenumber (β) is apparent at these frequencies denoting strong attenuation. In Figs. 4 (b) and (e), we have plotted the same values, however, although the chosen frequencies are still within the band gaps shown in Fig. 2, they are far from the resonant frequency. It is found that roughly half of the work done is temporarily stored in the first unit cell before being extracted by the negative work done at these two frequencies. However, the maximum work done is very small compared to those previously discussed in Figs. 4 (a) and (d), where the displacement amplitudes of the inner masses are extremely large near the resonant frequencies. The remaining half of the work done will then be transmitted or leaked to the proceeding EMMs. As predicted, it can be observed that the energy transmission will become low in the 5th cell and significantly lower in the 15th cell. That relatively weak attenuation ability coincides with what we found in Fig. 2, where small β is apparent at these two frequencies and more cells will be necessary to efficiently mitigate wave propagation. Finally, in Fig. 4 (c), the energy transmission behavior is found to be similar to that of a conventional non-dissipative material, where the negative work done is nearly absent and the energy within the inner masses is very low. This can be observed in the three energy transmission curves, where no wave attenuation is present.

Figure 4: Total work, total energy within the first unit cell and energy transmissions at the first, 5th and 15th unit cell at different frequencies of a non-dissipative mass-in-mass lattice system under a harmonic incidence: (a) 200Hz; (b) 700Hz; (c) 1500Hz; (d) 3000Hz; and (e) 4500Hz.

Fig. 5 plots the same energy parameters at identical frequencies as those in Fig. 4, however, damping coefficients are now included in the analysis in order to evaluate its influence on wave mitigation performance in the time domain. According to the dispersion analysis in Fig. 2, the wave behavior we are interested most is the emerging of band gaps through applying a proper damping coefficient on the innermost dashpot. Thus, in Fig. 5, the damping coefficients are given the following values: $\tau_1 = 0$, $\tau_2 = 0$ and $\tau_3 = 1$, other parameters are left unchanged as those in Fig. 4. It should be noted at this point that the axis of the energy in the figures is plotted logarithmically in order to make the smaller values visible on the graph. From Figs. 5 (a) – (e), we found that the wave energy flowing patterns for all the five frequencies within the two stop and one pass bands (572, 1000, 2000, 2490 and 3500 Hz) are almost identical. Obviously, the negative work done found in the non-dissipative EMM is almost entirely removed from the system at band gap frequencies. Both the total work done and the energy transmission through the first EMM is always increased as the increase of time. However, the total energy within the first EMM seems stable, and relatively extremely small compared with the difference between the total work done and the energy transmission the first EMM. The dissipated/absorbed energy within the first EMM from the damping is equal to the difference between the total work done and the summation of the total energy within the first EMM and the first EMM energy transmission. It is apparent that the dissipated energy is large and proportional to the total work done by the reaction force (40% – 50%). It can then be visualized and observed that the energy transmission through the 5th and 15th unit cells is very low, according to the dissipation ratio of the first EMM. Looking back at Fig. 5 (c), the pass band that occurs in the non-dissipative EMM has now become attenuated. This is due to the strong motions of the inner masses, where the damping presents. Overall, we see a substantial difference in wave attenuation behavior between the non-dissipative and dissipative metamaterials. The attenuation properties of the dissipative EMM have now been examined to be broadband in time domain, which coincides with what we found in Fig. 2 (d) and thus shows a potential in blast wave mitigation applications.

Figure 5: Total work, total energy within the first unit cell and energy transmissions at the first, 5th and 15th unit cell at different frequencies of a dissipative mass-in-mass lattice system under a harmonic incidence: (a) 200Hz; (b) 700Hz; (c) 1500Hz; (d) 3000Hz; and (e) 4500Hz.

Now that we move on to analysis for the dissipative EMM's potential applications for blast wave attenuation. Figure 6 shows a 1-D lattice system for blast wave transmission test, where 15 proposed dissipative EMMs are sandwiched between two background materials. The first 400 unit cells contain masses, m_1 , and springs, k_1 , are considered incident background material in the left side of the EMMs, and the last 385 identical unit cells are denoted as transmitted background material in the right side of the EMMs. Material parameters are the same as those used in Fig. 5. An incident blast wave is applied as a force signal to the first unit cell of the lattice system using the following equation

$$F = F_{\max} e^{-\frac{t-t_0}{t_d}} \quad (6)$$

where $F_{\max} = 1000$ N, $t_0 = 0.5$ ms, and $t_d = 0.1$ ms in order to realistically represent a typical air blast [9].

The frequency domain of the transmitted signal in the lattice system subjected to a blast pulse is calculated in Fig. 7 using the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) for understanding blast wave mitigation of the proposed EMM. It is apparent that for a non-dissipative conventional elastic material that no bandgaps are present, and the material lacks attenuation abilities across the analyzed frequency domain (solid curve). We see that the blast wave is broadband with frequencies from 0 to ~10 kHz with large amplitudes in the low frequency region and weak amplitudes in the higher frequency ranges. Moving on to the non-dissipative EMM (dashed curve), we can see two frequency amplitude dips present at approximately 600 - 1200 Hz and 2400 - 4500 Hz. The frequency regions of these two dips are in good agreement with the previous band gap frequency ranges shown in Fig. 2. Waves with frequency components within these two regions will be trapped into the EMM and cannot be propagated through. However, lots of the wave energy can still be transmitted through the EMM, when the frequency component falls between these two dips (i.e. 1200 - 2400 Hz). The dissipative EMM is then proposed to compensate this drawback. Analysis of the dissipative EMM results in a single broad amplitude dip that emerges the two non-dissipative amplitude dips and occupies the frequency range from approximately 400 Hz to 4500 Hz, which is in good agreement with the findings for the harmonic

analysis performed in Fig. 2. Waves with frequency components within this large attenuation region will mostly be absorbed in the innermost dashpot. It can be concluded that the dissipative EMM lattice system is an efficient tool for blast wave mitigation. Such concept will be adopted in a real dissipative EMM design in the next section.

Figure 6: 1-D dissipative mass-in-mass lattice system under a blast incidence.

Figure 7: Frequency domain of blast simulation calculated by Fast Fourier Transform.

3 DESIGN OF DISSIPATIVE EMMS FOR BLAST WAVE MITIGATION

In this section we propose a design and its application for blast wave mitigation by using the proposed dissipative EMM concept. We consider a plane strain problem with the unit cell design shown in Fig. 8 where material 1 represents the background material that allows for wave propagation. While material 1 represents our outside rigid mass, m_1 , and the spring, k_1 , the inner two rigid masses are represented by materials 3 and 5 and act as the resonators. material 2 and 4 represent two kinds of softer materials with damping properties, and are used as coatings to separate the rigid masses acting as springs and dashpots. Each material's thickness is denoted with a radial value from the center of the (cylindrical) coatings, R_n , where n denotes the particular layer of material ($n = 1, 2, 3$, or 4 from outside to inside). Each unit cell is given an overall length of L_1 , which represents the dimension of the Material 1 that the resonating and dissipative materials are imbedded in.

3.1 Dispersion calculation by Finite Element Method (FEM)

When carrying out conventional dispersion analysis with FEM, the eigenfrequencies are calculated based on the wavenumbers given in Bloch periodic boundary conditions. However, if damping is present, the eigenfrequencies obtained become complex due to the complex modulus. These complex eigenfrequencies cannot represent the overall wave attenuation in space. Additionally, when the damping coefficient is dependent on the frequency, procedures with conventional dispersion analysis will be extremely complicated and special iterative methods need to be developed. Therefore it is an objective to propose a wavenumber calculation method based on given frequencies for periodic structures with damped and/or frequency dependent material properties.

For the plane strain problem, the governing equation (Navier's equation) of motion expressed with displacements is

$$(\lambda + \mu)\nabla\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} + \mu\nabla^2\mathbf{u} = \rho\ddot{\mathbf{u}} \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{u} = [u_1, u_2]^T$, with u_1 and u_2 being the displacements in the x and y directions, ρ , λ and μ are material mass density, Lamé's first and second constants, respectively, and $\nabla^2 = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2}{\partial y^2}$.

By considering a primitive cell of the periodic problem and by using the Bloch theorem, the displacement can be assumed as [16]

$$\mathbf{u} = \tilde{\mathbf{u}} e^{i(\mathbf{k}\mathbf{x} + \omega t)} \quad (8)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{u}} = [\tilde{u}_1, \tilde{u}_2]^T$ is a periodic function with periodicity being L_1 , and $\mathbf{k} = [k_x, k_y]$ with k_x and k_y denoting the wavenumbers in x and y directions. By substituting Eq. (8) into Eq. (7) and letting $\mathbf{k} = [k \cos(\theta), k \sin(\theta)]$ with k and θ being total wavenumber and propagation direction, one can obtain

$$\mathbf{A}_2 \tilde{\mathbf{u}} k^2 + i \mathbf{A}_1 \nabla \tilde{\mathbf{u}} k + (\lambda + \mu) \nabla \nabla \cdot \tilde{\mathbf{u}} + \mu \nabla^2 \tilde{\mathbf{u}} + \rho \omega^2 \tilde{\mathbf{u}} = 0 \quad (9)$$

$$\text{where } \mathbf{A}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} -[(\lambda + 2\mu)\cos^2(\theta) + \mu\sin^2(\theta)] & -(\lambda + \mu)\cos(\theta)\sin(\theta) \\ -(\lambda + \mu)\cos(\theta)\sin(\theta) & -[(\lambda + 2\mu)\sin^2(\theta) + \mu\cos^2(\theta)] \end{bmatrix},$$

$$\mathbf{A}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 2(\lambda + 2\mu)\cos(\theta) & 2\mu\sin(\theta) & (\lambda + \mu)\sin(\theta) & (\lambda + \mu)\cos(\theta) \\ (\lambda + \mu)\sin(\theta) & (\lambda + \mu)\cos(\theta) & 2\mu\cos(\theta) & 2(\lambda + 2\mu)\sin(\theta) \end{bmatrix}.$$

For the finite element formulation of Eq. (9) COMSOL Multiphysics is adopted where the periodic boundary condition is applied on the outer boundaries of the unit cell. In order to obtain the dispersion relations of the proposed dissipative EMM, a quadratic eigenvalue problem for k is finally formulated and solved numerically.

Material Properties					
	Material 1	Material 2	Material 3	Material 4	Material 5
Lamé's First Constant (Pa)	2.0×10^9	5.0×10^5	2.0×10^{12}	2.0×10^5	2.0×10^{12}
Lamé's Second Constant (Pa)	1.0×10^9	2.5×10^5	1.0×10^{12}	1.0×10^5	1.0×10^{12}
Density (kg/m ³)	1000.0	1000.0	20000.0	1000.0	20000.0
Geometrical Parameters					
L_1 (mm)	R_1 (mm)	R_2 (mm)	R_3 (mm)	R_4 (mm)	
20.0	9.0	8.5	8.0	7.5	

Table 1. Material and geometric parameters of the proposed EMM

In Fig. 9 the dispersion relations of the longitudinal wave propagated through the proposed dissipative EMM with $\theta = 0$ are presented with the geometric and material properties listed in Table 1. According to the discussions in Sec. 2, two band gaps can be emerged into one large band gap through properly selecting the damping coefficient of the innermost dashpot. This merit behavior will be continually applied on the dissipative EMM design in this section. For the computational convenience of the application in the time domain analysis, Rayleigh damping coefficient, β_d , is adopted and applied to material 4. The relation between the loss factor and the Rayleigh damping is given as

$$\gamma_d = \omega \beta_d \quad (10)$$

For Fig. 9 (a) the real portion of the wavenumber has been plotted, which denotes the propagation of the longitudinal wave through the EMM. Similar to results presented in Fig. 2 (a), with zero Rayleigh damping there are two perfect band gaps present for the frequency ranges of approximately 400 – 1000Hz and 2200 – 3800Hz. This behavior is the same as a conventional non-dissipative EMM where the band gaps represent regions where there is no wave propagation. As the damping magnitude is increased, the band gaps are removed from the dispersion curve signifying wave propagation. For the imaginary portion of the wavenumber shown in Fig. 9 (b), we see the two separate wave attenuation regions present for little or no damping cases ($\beta_d = 0$ and 1×10^{-5}). As the Rayleigh damping is

increased to 1×10^{-4} and 1×10^{-3} , however, the attenuation region becomes broad, occupying a frequency range of approximately 400 to 3800 Hz, which implies that the band gap emerging concept presented in Sec. 2 has been realized through a simple coated EMM design.

Figure 8: Dissipative EMM coated with two resonators.

Figure 9: Dispersion relations of the dissipative EMM coated with two resonators.

3.2 Blast wave mitigation of the proposed dissipative EMM

In Fig. 10, we have constructed N number of unit cells sandwiched between incident and transmitted bars to examine blast wave mitigation of the proposed dissipative EMM similar to that which was presented in Fig. 6. The finite element based time domain analysis will be performed, where plane strain assumptions still hold. Material and geometrical parameters for the dissipative EMM have left unchanged from those used in Fig. 9. The material used in incident and transmitted bars is the background Material 1 in the dissipative EMM. A longitudinal incident force of the form, $F = F_0 e^{-\frac{t-t_0}{t_d}}$, is applied to the left edge of the incident bar to generate a blast wave, where $F_0 = 100$ N/m, $t_0 = 0.5$ ms and $t_d = 0.2$ ms. After the blast wave is travelling through the proposed dissipative EMM, the transmitted signal is then measured at a point 50 mm from the N -th cell. All the other outer edges are set free in the numerical simulations.

In Fig. 11, the frequency amplitude through FFT of the input and transmitted signals of the blast wave under transmission tests of the proposed EMM with different Rayleigh damping coefficients are given for unit cells: 5, 10 and 15. From Fig. 11 (a), where $N = 5$, we can see that the wave with frequency components within the band gaps can be successfully mitigated, when the Rayleigh damping is equal to zero, $\beta_d = 0$. Clearly, a pass band between the two band gaps can be also observed. It is worth to notice that the frequency range of wave attenuation is slightly higher than the width of the band gaps that were predicted in Fig. 9. When Rayleigh damping is applied (i.e. $\beta_d = 1 \times 10^{-4}$) to Material 4, the

wave attenuation becomes strong in the lower frequency region. Specifically, waves can be absorbed within the pass band frequencies, as predicted in Fig. 9. However, almost no changes are observed for higher frequency values than those that were seen when Rayleigh damping was absent ($\beta_d = 0$). When greater damping is applied (i.e. $\beta_d = 1 \times 10^{-3}$), waves can be adequately mitigated in the frequency range from 600 Hz to 5000 Hz. However, this range is slightly narrower than that in the two previous cases. In Figs. 11 (b) and (c), where $N = 10$ and 15 respectively, wave attenuation can be significantly improved in a broad frequency region. For example, waves can be almost completely absorbed at frequencies between 400 Hz and 4000 Hz, when $\beta_d = 1 \times 10^{-4}$ and 15 EMM unit cells are employed. The most efficient absorption characteristics usually coincide with large damping parameters, however, the attenuation band will become narrower for $\beta_d = 1 \times 10^{-3}$ compared with those when $\beta_d = 1 \times 10^{-4}$. Optimization design is still in need, as some extremely low frequency components will remain leaked to the proceeding system.

Figure 10: Dissipative EMM with two resonators under a blast incidence.

Figure 11: Frequency domain of the blast wave propagated through the proposed dissipative EMM: (a) $N = 5$; (b) $N = 10$; (c) $N = 15$.

4 SUMMARY

This paper presents a dissipative EMM with applications for effective blast wave mitigation. Dispersion relations were investigated where the influence of the inner two damping components were examined. Wave attenuation regions can be significantly enlarged by properly incorporating damping effect into the innermost spring. Numerical simulations demonstrated the efficiency of the proposed design for blast wave mitigation. According to this concept, we designed a coated dissipative elastic metamaterial with two resonators.

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